

Flavonoid Constituents of *Toddalia floribunda*

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*Toddalia floribunda*¹ Gamble (Rutaceae), a stout climbing shrub, occurs abundantly in Tirumala Hills of Andhra Pradesh, and Nilgiri and Pulney Hills of Tamilnadu. In the absence of any record of work on this plant we undertook the chemical examination of the whole plant.

Air-dried and powdered whole plant of *T. floribunda* (1.5 kg) was defatted with petroleum ether and then extracted with Me₂CO and MeOH. The acetone concentrate on purification over a column of silica gel gave two compounds A and B (CHCl₃-MeOH, 9:1) which were further separated by ppc (15% HOAc; R_f 0.62 and 0.10 respectively). Compound-A (80 mg), yellow needles from MeOH, m.p. 204–05° was identified as dihydrofisetin from its spectral data (ir, uv, ¹H nmr and mass) and by direct comparison with an authentic sample. Compound-B (0.12 g), yellow needles from MeOH, m.p. 258–59°, was characterised as diosmetin (luteolin 4'-methylether) from its colour reactions, spectral data (ir, uv, ¹H nmr and mass) and also by direct comparison with an authentic sample.

The yellow solid (0.7 g) obtained by the evaporation of MeOH extract was chromatographed over a column of silica gel (100–200 mesh) to yield compounds C (CHCl₃: EtOAc, 8:2 eluates)

and D (CHCl₃: EtOAc, 1:1 eluates). Compound-C (0.2 g), colourless needles from MeOH, m.p. 278–0°, was characterised as diosmin (diosmetin 7-O-rutinoside) from acid and enzymatic hydrolysis studies, spectral data and by direct comparison with an authentic sample. Compound-D (0.35 g), pale yellow needles from MeOH, m.p. 260–61°, was identified as hesperidin (hesperetin 7-O-rutinoside) from acid and enzymatic hydrolysis studies, spectral data (ir, uv, ¹H nmr and mass) and by direct comparison with an authentic sample.

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References

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Silver in Ayurvedic Pharmaceuticals—A Spectrophotometric Study using Sodium Pentamethylene Dithiocarbamate

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In continuation of our earlier work on the spectrophotometric determination of metal ions¹ through complexation with sodium pentamethylene dithiocarbamate (Pipdte) and extraction in chloroform, we report here a general method of determination of silver(I) including the effect of foreign ions and its application in the estimation of silver in Ayurvedic medicines.

Results and Discussion

Neither the reagent nor the metal ion have any absorbance at 320 nm. The complex was stable for more than 4 h and complete extraction could be achieved in a single extraction with 2 min of shaking in the presence of magnesium sulphate. Maximum absorbance was observed in the pH range 5–8 (NaAc/HAc). The influence of the